

The Sense of Duty and Responsibility in Chekhov's Uncle Vanya

Somnath B. Mahale

KAANMS Arts, Commerce and
Science College Satana,
Tal Baglan Dist. Nashik
goldsmith.somnath@gmail.com

We shall rest! We shall hear the angels; we shall see all Heaven lit with radiance; we shall see all earthly evil ;all our sufferings, drowned in mercy which will fill the whole world, and our life will be peaceful, gentle and sweet as a caress. I have faith, I have faith.

Anton Chekhov (1860-1904)

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Of all the world literature and their influence on the readers, the Russian literature stands out as the most realistic one to the reader from all the corners of the globe, the most true, beautiful, tragic, full of toil and the lessons from it. The play ends with these beautiful and touchy lines by Sonya, who feels that, the hard work and sufferings they have gone through will one day turn into happiness and this is the real meaning of life, what we lived for. Sonya recalls all the things right from the beginnings in what great troubles they had while earning every shilling in the era of the old Russian life. That these earnings were wasted on a professor who thinks that society reads his writings with great pleasure. On the contrary the society is not worried about his writings but the thought of daily earning.

One of the finest plays of the 19th century Russia, a social play by the Great Anton Chekhov deals with the lives of so many hardworking, compassionate and sensitive people in the society in Russia. This is a play different from all his other plays. He particularly points out the characters that are full of emotions, love, caring and sacrifice and a duty towards the society. We do feel sorry for the central character uncle Vanya, who over the years has worked very hard and supported his brother-in-law Sebryakov who is not bothered about the sacrifices done by Vanya, his old mother and Sonya. The professor is only worried about his status and thinking that his writing is helpful for the society. Another noticeable point is that Vanya accuses the professor for wasting all the money these people provided him by doing great toil and hard work and never thought of themselves. The devotedly supported him even when they difficulty

in living their own lives. Especially Sonia who had not a moment to spare for herself. Always busy in her work and giving hand to whoever wants her help. Uncle Vanya does the same thing and sometimes is fed up with the ideals of Sebryakov. Uncle Vanya is the most loved character in Chekhov's Play. The good qualities of Uncle Vanya can be seen and witnessed very minutely as we go on reading this beautiful play by Chekhov. It gives us immense pleasure to read the characteristics of human being, a hard worker and the love and compassion he feels for the fellow beings except that of Sebryankov. In true sense he is an example of a good natured man, and admirer of beauty and nature. He believes he is made for the work and nothing can stop him, his natural attachment with the people he is surrounded by. His love for the beautiful Yelena, the writer's wife and the longing he has for her is quite remarkable and praiseworthy yet there is a difference between his devotion and the type of work he does. His labour and the comradeship Anton Chekhov saw life, with its comedies and its tragedies, where few others before him had ever seen it. He found evil to rest precisely in the midst of idle talk, everyday pettiness, and people with nothing to distinguish them: neither vice nor virtue. But he found inviolable beauty too, strangely, among these same people when they were honest and courageous, and when they were not idle. Chekhov saw an ethical aesthetic beauty that the people he wrote of could not see. The result on the Chekhovian stage is a meandering stream of people searching for love, or excitement, or contentment, or dignity, when all the while it is directly at hand if one only could see and understand. The people that are surrounded in his garden having teas continuously and are all the time involved in their day-to-day life are very unique in itself. Chekhov's characters intrude upon the reader at first-even the informed reader who realizes that Chekhov's point in having them talk of their own self-consciousness. What a character says, in itself, is subordinate to who says it. Despite the apparent casualness with which Chekhov gives voice to his people, each speech is a minute insight into the fullness of the characters and the human in major part. These brush strokes which Chekhov paints from a nearly monochromatic pallet are what Stanislavsky referred to as the "intuition of feeling," the basis of the Moscow Art Theatre's success with Chekhov plays. And this is seen clearly when his plays were screened in theatre. The theatrically success was due to the fact that all his plays appealed the consciousness of the class of his generation. They not only loved them but they followed the types in their life. The character was so developed and depended heavily on minute ideas-hardly ideas at all-and tiny, significant speeches, much benefited when actually staged. No doubt such judgment is predicated on the acceptance of Chekhov the realist and the notion that real life holds no plots. For the sake of avoiding an argument that has no place

here, it is granted that life has no plots. However, as soon as a writer has a plan to present, albeit only a "slice of life," he has moulded, by the physical limitations of his art, if nothing else, a framework. Within that framework there is a beginning, there are conflicts, a climax, and there is an ending. The dramatic conflict in Chekhov is shifted to an inner plane and is not to be voiced in the exceptional, but in the commonplace. The conflict amounts to one of good but ineffectual people with the harsh crudeness of real life, a clash of the dream and the reality of an ordinary life. It is true that these conflicts are seldom revealed through highly dramatic action, but they are there and they are conveyed through the emotions, thoughts, and the attitude of the characters for one another. These complicated human relationships seldom resolve anything, seldom mean a radical change in the life of a character, but they do expose what Chekhov set out to expose: the contradictions and the contrariness of ordinary life. The same qualities can be seen in one of his earlier stories *An Antagonists*. In this story Chekhov simply characterizes the Dr Kirillov Zemstvo and Abogin. Their life is so complex and thereon the distress they both have in the difficult situation. The writer also says that the complex human behaviour is the most responsible for their troubles and hatred, misery for the human being. Time will pass, and Kirillov's grief will pass, but the unjust attitude, unworthy of human heart, will not pass, but will remain with the doctor till the day of his death. The subject matter of Chekhov's plays is the subject matter of life, and is as complicated and at the same time as simple as in real life. His two principal themes are courage and hope, and the destruction of beauty by those who are blind to it. Both can be found in *Uncle Vanya*. It is a spiritual beauty, not a physical one that Chekhov endorses, however. That is not to say there are no physically beautiful people in Chekhov's world, nor is it to say that the spiritually beautiful always come out better than the others. The criterion of beauty is best expressed by Astrov in *Uncle Vanya*. Speaking of Helena Andreyevna, he says: A human being should be entirely beautiful: the face, the clothes, the mind, the thoughts. She is, of course, beautiful to look at, but... she does nothing but sleep and eat and walk and bewitch us, and this surprises the reader, whenever she comes across Vanya she feels an enchanting person to him and he also adores and confesses her many a times. And that is all. She has no responsibilities; everything is done for her . . . and an idle life can never be a pure one. And they all are affected by the presence and the idleness of the beautiful, charming Yelena. They all feel that because of her they have all lost their creativity and she is like a hindrance to them even if she is a charming young woman. Dr Astrov who is always looking after the sick ones feels it sharply. Soniya is plain in *Uncle Vanya*. As the story moves on the differences Sonia and Yelena had are slowly disappeared. They even sit side by

side and discuss about the coming days. Yelena infact advises Sonia to marry physician Astrov. But Astrov doesn't have any feelings for the young Sonia. Both have the strong desire for the happy life and at the same time aware that it is very difficult to have it. Sonia, is the embodiment of courage and spiritual beauty, for whom Chekhov wrote his most radiant passage at the end of Uncle Vanya. As he talks, Astrov is blind to the very qualities of beauty about which he speaks. Helena, the physically beautiful, does. She will follow her husband, other men will fall in love with her, she will continue to be bored and idle. Despite the destructive spirit of which Astrov accuses her, she above all others must be given credit for maintaining human dignity because she more than anyone else was most often tempted to fall. Astrov survives, because he comes to his senses. He goes back, a cynic, to nature which he trusts. He mistrusts people, but leaves with a flippant remark, "*E finita la commedia!*"-so ends the comedy. Nothing can surprise him anymore; he will not again run the risk of losing his head or his dignity in the complicated relationships of human beings. Sonya survives, and the same faith and courage which sustain her will sustain her Uncle Vanya. His dejection and broken heart will be mended by continued honest work, and patience and faith. These three, Astrov, Sonya, and Vanya, will never be the same after the Serebrakoffs' visit, their relations with each other will be changed, but life will go on, and they will continue to live it. In the melodramatic Wood Demon, nearly everyone will live "happily ever after," although it took the suicide of Voynitsky (Uncle Vanya) to bring them to their senses. Perhaps Chekhov's strongest intent was to show that life does go on, despite the shocking death of a member of the family. However, the picnic in the final scene, and the reunion of Elena and Serebrakoff are somewhat too brazen and flippant for these sensitive people. Conversely, in such a play it is just as logical that the people find happiness for themselves as it is for Chekhov to show that their unhappiness was a result of defects in their character. But this kind of logic was not what Chekhov had intended, as he attested to by withdrawing the play immediately. In Uncle Vanya it is not so much the personal defects of character that cause unhappiness as it is the pressures and tensions on everyday country life created by economic and social conditions of the time. It is the boring, stupefying, and vulgar life in the country which drags down talented and intelligent people like Astrov and Uncle Vanya and Sonya and Serebrakoff to the level of pettiness and selfishness. Only when the truth is out does the character of a person show itself-in the frustration of Uncle Vanya, in the cynicism of Astrov, in the retreat to faith of Sonya, in the retreat per se of the professor. Professor Serebrakoff is not a villain. He is unable to deal with life and can live only in the belief that his work is contributing to the general good of humanity. At last Sonia convinces

uncle Vanya that their troubles would be soon over and will have a good, peaceful and happy life they longed for.

At the end we can conclude the paper by adding, that the most striking point in studying the Russian literature is that it is very much dear to our heart. The life they lived was the toughest on and we feel for them and these human emotions are close to our heart. It makes us understand and follow the good life and that one day we'll have peace and everything will pass and our life will be happy in every sense.

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Quotation from Leoncavallo's *Pagliacci*.